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Resilience of Higher Education Institutions to Security Risks – Analysis of the Current State and the Need for Cooperation

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ABSTRACT

Educational institutions should inherently embody the values and directions that a society and state aspire to follow, while also playing an expert role in shaping not only educational policies but broader societal policies as well. However, as societies today face various challenges and threats, the educational system is not exempt from the negative phenomena shaping contemporary events and processes. Rapid global political shifts, conflicts, internal social violence, cyber threats, and other risks necessitate that the education system, through both formal and informal educational content, equips students, pupils, and even adults with the necessary knowledge to respond adequately to crises. A literature review on risk management in higher education yields limited results (Raanan, 2009), with most studies focusing on teaching risk management to students or practitioners, such as those by Menoni (2006) and Gabel (2008). To assess the preparedness of higher education institutions (HEIs) and their employees for various security risks, we conducted a study as part of the project activity “Enhancing the Capacities of Higher Education Institutions for Various Security Risks”, under the Erasmus CBHE programme.

KEYWORDS

HEI; risk; knowledge; cooperation, resilience; analysis, management.

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1. Introduction

Beyond the fact that the right to education and education itself are enshrined in the foundational documents of international organizations and national regulations, education, through a well-defined and structured system, remains the most effective and, particularly today, the most relevant means of acquiring knowledge and skills. While mass media, the internet, and social networks undoubtedly influence the formation of attitudes, the dissemination of various information (regardless of its accuracy and quality), and often have a detrimental impact on behavior, particularly among young people, the education system is the entity that systematically and methodically provides knowledge and shapes values among children and youth. Schools and individual teachers, alongside families, the media, and peer groups, exert a significant influence on the development of young people's values and, consequently, on society as a whole (Halsted, 1996, p. 3).

Educational institutions should inherently embody the values and directions that a society and state aspire to follow, while also playing an expert role in shaping not only educational policies but also broader societal policies. Education and upbringing, although institutionally and programmatically separated in specific systems, are in fact inseparable elements—not only as a function of state duties but also as integral aspects of every individual's life (Bošković, 2012, p. 199). Due to its importance, not only in shaping individuals' knowledge and personalities but also in lifelong learning, some authors emphasize that “many groups in society have a legitimate right to participate in the educational process—parents, employers, politicians, local communities, industry leaders, taxpayers, as well as teachers and children themselves. Within each of these groups, there is a wide diversity of political, social, economic, religious, ideological, and cultural values” (Halsted, 1996, p. 3). Collaboration in designing optimal educational programs and knowledge dissemination methods is undoubtedly desirable. As some scholars argue, “the educational system in modern society should enrich individuals with knowledge that enables their participation in political and economic life, while also providing opportunities for social networking” (Durkheim, 1922; Labaree, 1977). Schools also have the capacity to build communities that can reduce impacts of hazards, withstand the brunt of disaster and enable members to become “assets” rather than “liabilities” through proper knowledge dissemination and committed engagement with the members of the community in fully utilizing the resources which could increase the capacity of a community to recover after a disaster and promote resilience (Ahmed, 2025; Cvetković, 2023; Cvetković et al., 2024; Garba et al., 2025; Goyal, 2019; Jevtić et al., 2025; Milenković et al., 2024; Pradhan et al., 2025; Rico, 2019, pp.46-47).

However, as societies today face various challenges and threats, the educational system is not exempt from the negative phenomena shaping contemporary events and processes. Challenging issues that are anthropogenically related, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, Wildfires, Droughts, Flooding, heat waves, Epidemic outbreaks, and Terrorism, can all lead to large-scale consequences for the nation and its communities (Dukiya, 2021, p. 12). Rapid global political shifts, conflicts, internal social violence, cyber threats, and other risks necessitate that the education system, through both formal and informal educational content, equips students, pupils, and even adults with the necessary knowledge to respond adequately to crises. A wider, less professional public lacks sufficient expertise to comprehend the risks of emergencies (Cvetkovic, 2019, p. 82). Curricula and educational programs must not be static and immutable but should remain adaptive to new insights and challenges faced by all members of society. Increasingly, global policymakers, researchers, and educators at all levels are focusing on approaches that encourage individuals to become agents of change toward sustainability (Orlović Lovren, 2021, p. 41).

While an environment of constant change and disruption creates opportunities for institutions to specialize within a crowded marketplace, it also generates an increasing range of risks that can rapidly destabilize their strategic planning (Deloitte Ltd, 2017, p. 2). Despite the ongoing discussions in both theory and practice about educational content, reforms, and the selection of the most effective methodological approaches, little research exists on how educational institutions themselves are exposed to security risks and their preparedness to manage emergencies. While academic institutions have traditionally educated others on risk management, relatively little effort has been made to apply this knowledge to their own operations (Raanan, 2009).

A literature review on risk management in higher education yields limited results (Raanan, 2009), with most studies focusing on teaching risk management to students or practitioners, such as those by Menoni (2006) and Gabel (2008). Only a minimal number of authors examine risks inherent to academic institutions themselves (Raanan, 2009). Interestingly, research on risk management in educational institutions—notably higher education—tends to be published either by insurance companies addressing financial and economic emergency risks or by authors specializing in financial risks. Query (2000), for instance, explores what could be termed “insured risks,” including workplace accidents, sexual harassment, student substance abuse, and employment policies. Hargreaves (2008) quantifies the risks associated with desired learning outcomes and faculty turnover through curriculum analysis. Resilience to and recovery from disasters have been studied by various groups and governments to reduce the toll of disasters and increase their recovery capacity (Rico, 2019, 9.46).

A notable exception involves scholars studying school shootings—tragedies in which young individuals perpetrate mass violence against their peers and teachers, such as Kucher (2022) and Cheryl (2017). However, most of these studies focus on profiling perpetrators of mass violence rather than analyzing the broader spectrum of risks faced by educational institutions. Apart from everyday hazards such as household fires, gas leaks, and physical injuries, universities encounter additional specialized risks, including those arising from flammable liquids, laboratory equipment, and other hazardous materials (Bush, 1976). Furthermore, both educational facilities and staff face various risks, ranging from natural disasters (earthquakes, severe storms) to human-induced threats (workplace harassment, injuries, discrimination, and cyberattacks).

Until the enactment of the Health and Safety at Work Act in 1975, only a few universities had formalized safety policies (Bush, 1976, p. 1369). While violent acts, such as school shootings, naturally command persistent attention from researchers due to their shocking nature, other risks—such as fires, structural collapses, psychological and verbal harassment, and sexual abuse—are no less probable or impactful within educational institutions. Raanan (2009) categorized risks in higher education institutions, identifying several key types: ethical risks, violence and other security threats, competition, poor governance, financial risks, laboratory and equipment quality, and legal risks (Raanan, 2009, pp. 44–45).

The willingness of stakeholders to accept an honest assessment of risk factors within institutions is a critical element of risk management. Understanding the existing risk tolerance levels of governments, students, and other stakeholders could help institutions define their risk appetite and determine which risks require management and how they should be managed (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2005, p. 12). Given the previously emphasized and unequivocal significance of education, cooperation among scholars—as well as between academia and external institutions—would not only highlight the complexity and dynamism of these challenges but also guide educators in preparing students to face them and ensure that educational institutions are equipped to manage potential crises.

A disruption in the functioning of the education system or an inadequate response to an emergency not only affects the institution in question—it also undermines public trust in education, science, and academic processes. “The violence that young people in Baltimore are exposed to is symptomatic of the increasingly distressing conditions within their communities... As one response, schools across Baltimore are working with families and communities to create safer environments where children can live, learn, and grow” (Sanders, 1996, pp. 369–370).

2. Methodological Framework of the Research

To assess the preparedness of higher education institutions (HEIs) and their employees for various security risks, a study was conducted as part of the project “Enhancing the Capacities of Higher Education Institutions for Various Security Risks. The research took place between November and December 2024 and consisted of two main activities:

1. Analysis of the existence of various regulatory acts governing occupational health and safety, anti-discrimination policies, fire protection, and other security-related matters within HEIs in Serbia.

2. Surveying HEI employees through anonymous questionnaires

The study covered 32 HEIs, including 19 public and 13 private faculties. Among them, 15 faculties specialized in social sciences and humanities, 12 in natural and mathematical sciences, 3 in medical sciences, and 3 in the field of arts. The survey was completed by 26 PhD holders, four individuals with master's degrees, and two respondents with a bachelor's degree.

The research aimed to evaluate HEIs' preparedness for various security risks, both in terms of the existence of necessary legal documents and in practical terms, by analyzing employees' knowledge and perceptions of their institutions' resilience and their cooperation with other organizations to achieve greater security.

The primary hypothesis stated that HEIs in Serbia are not fully resilient or prepared for various security risks. The secondary hypotheses were as follows:

- a) HEIs do not have all relevant legal acts related to institutional security adopted and publicly available.
- b) There is no adequate level of employee training on emergency response, nor is there sufficient collaboration with other institutions to improve resilience and crisis response.

In relation to laws relevant to the safe operation of higher education institutions (HEIs)—including the Law on Higher Education, the Labor Law, the Law on Occupational Health and Safety, the Fire Protection Law, the Personal Data Protection Law, the Whistleblower Protection Law, the Criminal Code, and the Anti-Discrimination Law—this study analyzed whether HEIs have adopted the necessary sub-legal acts and whether these documents are publicly available on the official websites of the faculties to ensure transparency.

In the part of the study involving survey responses from HEI employees, the independent variable was the faculty's ownership structure (public or private). In contrast, the dependent variables, measured through the questionnaire, assessed employees' perceptions of institutional resilience to security risks and their awareness of whether cooperation with other HEIs and relevant state institutions exists.

The questionnaire consisted of a combination of open-ended and closed-ended questions, with the closed-ended questions addressing variables such as education level, ownership type, and the faculty's scientific or artistic field, as well as the following key aspects:

1. "Does your institution have all the necessary sub-legal acts (regulations, guidelines) governing occupational health and safety, emergency response procedures (fire, earthquake), personal data protection, anti-discrimination policies, and workplace mobbing prevention measures?"
2. "Have you or your colleagues experienced violations of security-related measures, procedures, or laws regarding employee protection (workplace mobbing, discrimination, verbal or physical assault, inadequate working conditions)?"
3. (If the answer to the previous question was "Yes") "Did you initiate legal proceedings regarding employee protection, and if not, what were the reasons?"
4. "Are regular employee training sessions and knowledge assessments on fire protection conducted in accordance with legal and sub-legal regulations?"
5. "Are regular employee health check-ups conducted in accordance with job descriptions and prescribed legal frameworks?"
6. "Do you believe that researchers from different HEIs, through their knowledge and experience, can contribute to enhancing security in public administration, governmental institutions, and society in general?"
7. "Does an emergency at your institution affect its regular operations?"
8. "How would you rate the resilience and preparedness of your institution (employees and material resources) for the following crises?"

9. "To what extent do you believe that collaboration with relevant governmental bodies or local authorities in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises is necessary for your institution?"
10. "To what extent do you believe that collaboration with other HEIs in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises is necessary for your institution?"

This methodological framework was designed to assess the extent to which HEIs in Serbia are prepared for various security risks, both in terms of existing legal frameworks and practical implementation, and to explore the role of inter-institutional and governmental cooperation in strengthening institutional resilience.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Regulatory Acts

As part of this research, we identified a set of regulatory acts that higher education institutions (HEIs) should possess, implement, and publicly disclose on their official websites. These acts are intended to enhance the security of employees, students, third parties, and the institutions themselves, addressing a wide range of potential risks. The following documents were identified as essential:

1. Risk Assessment Act for the Workplace
2. Fire Protection Act and Regulation
3. Personal Data Protection Regulation
4. Regulation on Information of Public Importance
5. Regulation on the Gender Equality Officer
6. Code of Professional Ethics

A review of official websites of 19 public and 12 private faculties yielded the following results:

- a) None of the HEIs has publicly disclosed all of the listed acts.
- b) The Risk Assessment Act for the Workplace is publicly available at 50% of HEIs (10 public and six private faculties).
- c) The Fire Protection Act and Regulation are publicly available at 10% of HEIs (3 public faculties).
- d) The Personal Data Protection Regulation is publicly available at 50% of HEIs (11 public and five private faculties).
- e) The Regulation on Information of Public Importance is publicly available at 30% of HEIs (8 public and two private faculties).
- f) The Regulation on the Gender Equality Officer is publicly available at 10% of HEIs (3 public faculties).
- g) The Code of Professional Ethics is publicly available at 20% of HEIs (4 public and two private faculties)

The absence of these acts on the official websites of faculties does not necessarily mean that they do not exist. However, making these acts public and accessible to anyone who wishes to review them would demonstrate transparency in matters of security and in the protection of employees, students, and third parties from various risks. Public availability of these acts would facilitate access for employees, students, and third parties present at HEIs, enabling them to become familiar with their rights, protection procedures against specific dangers or inappropriate incidents, and the appropriate channels for exercising their rights and submitting potential complaints.

3.2. Survey on Attitudes

The survey was conducted using Google Forms, with the questionnaire distributed via a link. A total of 32 respondents, all employees at HEIs, participated – 19 from public faculties and 13 from

private faculties. The respondents included 16 male and 16 female participants, and their age distribution is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Age Distribution of Respondents (Expressed in Percentages).

The responses to the questions will be presented in tabular form, structured according to the independent variable—faculty ownership type.

Table 1 displays the responses to the question: “Does your institution have all the necessary sub-legal acts (regulations, guidelines) governing occupational health and safety, emergency response procedures (fire, earthquake), personal data protection, anti-discrimination policies, and workplace mobbing prevention measures?” The available response options were: *Fully*, *Partially*, *Insufficiently*, *Not at all*, and *I do not know*.

Table 1. Responses to the question: “Does your institution have all the necessary sub-legal acts (regulations, guidelines) governing occupational health and safety, emergency response procedures (fire, earthquake), personal data protection, anti-discrimination policies, and workplace mobbing prevention measures?”

Faculties/responses	Fully	Partially	Insufficiently	Not at all	I do not know
Public faculty	10	5	0	0	4
Private faculty	4	8	0	0	1

The responses indicate that the majority of respondents (14, or 40.2%) believe and/or are aware that their HEI has all the necessary legal acts in place. A slightly smaller portion (13, or 30.9%) stated that their institution partially possesses these acts, while five respondents (1.5%) answered that they do not know. None of the respondents indicated that their HEI lacks any legally required acts or has an insufficient number of them. These responses support the previously stated finding that HEIs

may have adopted all necessary legal acts but have not published them on their official websites. This lack of publication indicates reduced transparency and limited access for interested parties, rather than a lack of preparedness, at least in the legislative aspect.

Tables 2 and 3 present the responses to the following questions:

- “Have you or your colleagues experienced violations of security-related measures, procedures, or laws regarding employee protection (workplace mobbing, discrimination, verbal or physical assault, inadequate working conditions)?”
- “Did you initiate legal proceedings regarding employee protection, and if not, what were the reasons?”

Table 3 includes only the responses of participants who had previously answered “Yes” to the first question.

Table 2. Structure of responses to the question: “Have you or your colleagues experienced violations of security-related measures, procedures, or laws regarding employee protection (workplace mobbing, discrimination, verbal or physical assault, inadequate working conditions)?” (absolute numbers).

Faculties/responses	Yes, personally	Yes, together with my colleagues	No, but my colleagues have	No, I have not
Public faculty	9	4	4	2
Private faculty	3	1	3	6

Table 3. Structured responses to the question: “Did you initiate legal proceedings regarding employee protection, and if not, what were the reasons?” (absolute numbers)

Faculties/responses	No, because such issues have not been addressed in the past.	The administration has disputed every similar procedure.	No, I initiated legal actions through a lawyer.	I did not want to.
Public faculty	4	3	3	3
Private faculty	1	1	0	2

Some form of violation of measures or procedures related to occupational health and safety, non-discrimination, or workplace mobbing was personally experienced—either individually or together with colleagues—by 13 respondents from public faculties and four from private faculties. Additionally, the majority of respondents employed at public faculties reported that at least one of their colleagues had experienced one of the aforementioned issues.

A total of 6 employees from private faculties reported not experiencing any of these violations, compared to only two from public faculties. Respondents who answered “Yes, personally” or “Yes, together with my colleagues” to this question were then given an open-ended question asking whether they had reported the incident(s) or initiated a legal procedure to protect their rights.

The responses were qualitatively analyzed for content and meaning and categorized into four structured categories.:

1. “No, because such issues have not been addressed in the past.” - “No, because it is pointless.” “No, because no one wants to deal with such matters.” “No, because based on others’ experiences, I see that it is futile.”
2. “The administration has disputed every similar procedure.” - “No, because it was made clear in advance that such cases would not be considered.” “No, because attempts to report are rendered meaningless.” “No, because the administration minimizes incidents.” “No, because the other party disputes the events.”

3. "No, I initiated legal actions through a lawyer."- "I hired a lawyer for a private lawsuit." "I attempted a settlement through a lawyer." "I immediately hired a lawyer."
4. "I did not want to." "No, because it was an isolated incident." "No, because we resolved the issue informally." "I did not want to deal with it."

Regardless of the exact wording of their responses, the majority (40.2%) indicate that victims of some form of harassment, workplace mobbing, or violations of occupational health and safety rights did not wish to officially report the issue to the administration or relevant personnel at their HEI. The primary reason for this reluctance appears to be the belief – or prior experience as witnesses – that such reports are dismissed and incidents are disputed.

Table 4 presents the responses to questions regarding measures whose mandatory and periodic implementation is prescribed by law, specifically related to employee training for fire emergency response and employee health examinations.

Table 4. Responses to the questions: "Are regular employee training sessions and knowledge assessments on fire protection conducted in accordance with legal and sub-legal regulations?" and "Are regular employee health examinations conducted in accordance with job descriptions and prescribed legal frameworks?" (absolute numbers).

Are regular employee training sessions and knowledge assessments on fire protection conducted in accordance with legal and sub-legal regulations?			
FACULTIES/RESPONSES	Yes, regularly	Not regularly	No
Public faculty	17	1	1
Private faculty	6	5	2
Are regular employee health examinations conducted in accordance with job descriptions and prescribed legal frameworks?			
FACULTIES/RESPONSES	Yes, regularly	Not regularly	No
Public faculty	12	5	2
Private faculty	5	5	3

The responses presented in Table 4 indicate that, for the most part, employee training and knowledge assessments on fire emergency response, as well as mandatory periodic health examinations, are conducted in accordance with the legally prescribed methods and timeframes. However, these measures are more consistently implemented at public faculties than at private ones. Nevertheless, it is concerning that 16 respondents reported that these two types of measures are conducted irregularly. In comparison, as many as eight respondents reported that they are not conducted at all. Given that these trainings and measures are mandated by law and directly affect employees' preparedness for fire emergencies and their health in relation to their job roles, their implementation is crucial to HEIs' overall preparedness for emergencies. The failure or irregular implementation of these activities not only violates legal requirements but also reduces institutional resilience to specific security risks.

Figure 2 presents the responses to the question: "Does an emergency at your institution affect its regular operations?" The available response options were: "Yes, fully," "Yes, significantly," "Yes, slightly," and "No, it does not."

Figure 2. Responses of all respondents on the impact of various emergencies on the regular operations of their HEIs.

Figure 2 presents all respondents' answers, regardless of the HEI where they work, to provide insight into their perceptions of how specific emergencies and security risks can disrupt their institutions' regular operations. The analysis of all responses indicates that the most significant adverse impacts would come from strikes, earthquakes, fires, floods, and epidemics. At the same time, other weather disasters and cyberattacks on institutional systems would have a partial detrimental effect. This question allowed respondents to select multiple answers from a list of predefined threats.

Regarding institutional ownership, employees at public faculties identified the following risks as significantly or moderately affecting institutional operations: strikes (10 respondents), fires (8 respondents), epidemics (9 respondents), and cyberattacks (6 respondents). Meanwhile, employees at private faculties reported the following threats as having the most significant impact: earthquakes (5 respondents), fires (7 respondents), and epidemics (7 respondents). Additionally, they identified moderate risks from cyberattacks (3 respondents), other natural disasters (2 respondents), and strikes (1 respondent).

The majority of respondents perceive earthquakes and fires as the most severe emergencies. However, employees at public HEIs also consider strikes a major disruptive factor, whereas only one respondent from a private faculty mentioned strikes as a significant issue. Cyberattacks and system intrusions are generally perceived as less disruptive to HEIs' regular operations. However, such attacks can result in the theft of employees' and students' personal data, potentially damaging the institution's reputation and disrupting student services and record-keeping systems.

Figure 3 presents respondents' answers to the question: "How would you rate the resilience and preparedness of your institution (employees and material resources) for the following crises?" The identified risks included: a) Verbal and physical violence against employees, b) Threats involving weapons, c) Fires and explosions, d) Earthquakes, e) Workplace mobbing, f) Discrimination, g) Food poisoning. The rating scale ranged from "1" (insufficient preparedness) to "5" (fully satisfactory preparedness).

Figure 3. Respondents' ratings (from 1 to 5) on the resilience and preparedness of their HEIs for various risks

Respondents assigned the highest ratings (4 and 5) to their HEIs' preparedness regarding the following risks: fires and explosions, workplace mobbing, discrimination, and food poisoning. Conversely, lower ratings (1, 2, and 3) were given for risks such as verbal and physical violence against employees, threats involving weapons, and earthquakes. Employees at public faculties rated their institutions highest in terms of resilience and preparedness for fires and explosions, food poisoning,

and discrimination. However, this presents a certain contradiction with their responses to previous questions, in which some reported experiencing mobbing, discrimination, or violations of safety measures. In contrast, others indicated that fire response training and knowledge assessments were irregular or nonexistent. Employees at private faculties gave the highest ratings to their institutions' resilience and preparedness for verbal and physical violence, discrimination, and food poisoning. For preparedness against weapon-related threats, both public and private faculty employees gave an average rating of 3.

Table 5 presents the responses to three questions that share a common theme—the need for cooperation among HEIs, the impact of knowledge, research, and academic personnel on overall security improvement in society, and collaboration with state and local government bodies to strengthen institutional capacities and resilience.

Table 5. Respondents' answers to the following questions: 1) "Do you believe that researchers from different higher education institutions, through their knowledge and experience, can contribute to improving security in public administration, governmental institutions, and society in general?" 2) "To what extent do you consider collaboration with relevant state administration or local government bodies in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises necessary for your institution?" and 3) "To what extent do you consider collaboration with other higher education institutions in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises necessary for your institution?"

Table 5. Participants' answers.

"Do you believe that researchers from different higher education institutions, through their knowledge and experience, can contribute to improving security in public administration, governmental institutions, and society in general?"			
FACULTIES/RESPONSES	Yes	No	Partially
Public faculty	16	1	2
Private faculty	8	1	4
"To what extent do you consider collaboration with relevant state administration or local government bodies in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises necessary for your institution?"			
FACULTIES/RESPONSES	Necessary	Partially necessary	Not necessary
Public faculty	10	7	2
Private faculty	10	1	2
"To what extent do you consider collaboration with other higher education institutions in training and capacity-building for resilience to various risks and crises necessary for your institution?"			
FACULTIES/RESPONSES	Necessary	Partially necessary	Not necessary
Public faculty	8	9	2
Private faculty	6	5	2

The analysis of responses in Table 5 shows that the majority of employees at both public and private faculties believe that HEIs, through their resources, can help enhance the security of other institutions and society as a whole. Additionally, they consider collaboration with state and local government bodies to enhance institutional preparedness and resilience to be both desirable and necessary. A slightly smaller number of respondents indicated that such collaboration with other HEIs is necessary. A total of six respondents stated that no collaboration with state institutions or other faculties is needed. Although faculties, by their structure, education, and the qualifications of their employees (teaching staff), can be considered specialized in specific scientific disciplines, including security, law, and environmental studies—fields directly related to the real-world risks

examined in this study—employees at both public and private faculties essentially believe that cooperation with state institutions, rather than with other HEIs, would better contribute to their preparedness and resilience to various risks. At the same time, and somewhat paradoxically, the majority of respondents from both public and private HEIs believe that faculties, due to their expertise, can help improve overall security in society.

4. Conclusion

The analysis of the research indicates that, according to respondents' responses, the majority of higher education institutions (HEIs) have regulatory acts in place to protect employees, students, and institutional facilities from various physical, natural, technical, or social risks. However, most of these acts are not available on the faculties' official websites, making it difficult for interested parties to familiarize themselves with their content, including their rights, obligations, restrictions, and protection measures in the event of various incidents or emergencies. Although legally mandated, health assessments for employees and fire emergency training are not regularly conducted or are absent at some faculties, primarily at privately owned institutions. Respondents identified fires, earthquakes, and strikes as the most disruptive risks to their institutions' functioning. In contrast, cyberattacks, other natural disasters, and food poisoning (in institutions with cafeterias) were perceived as less disruptive. At the same time, respondents consider their institutions to be most vulnerable to armed threats, physical and verbal aggression among employees, and fires. Despite these findings, 20.4% of respondents believe that collaboration with relevant state institutions or local government bodies is not necessary to enhance HEI resilience. By comparison, 40.2% believe that such collaboration with other faculties is also unnecessary to achieve the same goal.

Indeed, employee education and training are welcome. In many situations, it seems protocol-driven, formal, and many perceive it as challenging or even a waste of time. Therefore, there is a degree of resistance. The fact is, as we have witnessed in recent events, that although there are adequate regulations and legal frameworks, the bureaucratic apparatus sometimes does not respond appropriately, precisely, or clearly.

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